

Comparing The Acromio-Axillo Suprasternal Notch With Modified Mallampati Test To Predict Difficult Tracheal Intubation In Adults In Supine Position

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Abstract

Background: In this study we propose to compare the diagnostic efficacy of novel criteria, AASI in relation with MMT, in predicting the challenging visibility of the larynx during endotracheal intubation in patients receiving general anesthesia.

Methods: This prospective observational study was conducted in the department of anesthesia at Trichy Medical College Hospital and Research Center, among 300 cases undergoing surgery with general anesthesia. Patients aged 18-60 years from both genders and ASA class I and II were included in the study. A total of 300 cases were included in the study. SPSS was used to analyze the data.

Results: In this study based on age, there were 7%, 28.3%, 34%, and 30.7% of cases belongs to 18-30 years, 31-40 years, 41-50 years and 51-60 years, respectively. Also there were 59.3% male and 40.7% female participants included. Based on MMT grades, there were 67%, 19%, 10.3% and 3.7% of cases belong to grade 1, grade 2, grade 3 and grade 4 respectively. Similarly, there were 88.3% of cases had AASI ≤ 0.5 and 11.7% of cases had AASI > 0.5 . On assessing the association between MMT and AASI in order to predict the difficult intubation, there was a statistically significant association noted. On assessing the efficacy of AASI in predicting difficult intubation, Sn, Sp, PPV, NPV and diagnostic efficacy were reported as 95.9%, 88.6%, 98.5%, 73.8% and 95% respectively.

Conclusion: AASI is a new yet helpful test to gauge how difficult laryngoscopic visualization will be during tracheal intubation. The relationship between AASI and difficult laryngoscopic visualization is demonstrated in this study, which indicates that higher AASI is likely associated with higher Cormack-Lehane grades and anesthesiologist discomfort.

Key words: AASI, MMT, difficult intubation, laryngeal view

INTRODUCTION

When airway issues are found during the preanesthetic assessment, the anesthetist can make plans to minimize the risk of complications, which leads to the safest airway care¹. There is variation in the occurrence of difficult airway; reports range from 1.5% to 20%². Based on an examination of adverse respiratory events in the ASA database, the majority of events related to the airways have the potential to cause death or brain injury³. Simple anatomical landmarks are employed in conventional tests for difficult airway prediction that are often used in daily practice, such as the modified Mallampati test (MMT), thyromental distance (TMD), and upper lip bite test (ULBT)^{4,5}. Simple as these bedside screening procedures are, accurate performance and assessment of the results depend on the patient's cooperation. When used alone, the well accepted predictors of difficult airway exhibit low to moderate discrimination. When both tools are used, this may get even better^{6,7}.

AASI is a bedside test that uses surface anatomy and was first suggested by Kamranmanesh et al⁸. Direct visualization of the larynx (DVL) has been proposed as a reliable predictor of AASI, a relatively novel test based on surface land mark. It has been noted that DVL was seen in those whose necks were buried deep in their chests. Therefore, the area of the arm-chest junction above the suprasternal notch may serve as a DVL indicator. Patients with deep-chested necks were found to have DVL; these patients were also classified as having a sloping clavicle. They suggested a new index called the AASI and used the part of the arm-chest junction above the level of the suprasternal notch to estimate DVL⁸. Keeping these in mind, the purpose of this study was to compare AASI with MMP and assess how well this new test may predict DVL.

METHODS

This prospective observational study was conducted in the department of anesthesia at Trichy Medical College Hospital and Research Center, among 300 cases undergoing surgery with general anesthesia. Patients aged 18-60 years from both genders and ASA class I and II were included in the study. A total of 300 cases were included in the study. AASI was calculated with the patients lying in supine position and their upper extremities resting by the side, AASI was calculated based on the following measurements: Using a ruler a vertical line was drawn from the top of the acromion process to the superior border of the axilla at the pectoralis major

muscle; A second line was drawn perpendicular to line A from the suprasternal notch; The portion of line A that lies above the point at which line B intersected line A was line C. AASI was calculated by dividing the length of line C by that of line A ($AASI = C/A$).

SPSS version 20 was used to do analysis. Mc Namer test was used to compare the sensitivity and specificity of both the methods. p value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

In this study based on age, there were 7%, 28.3%, 34%, and 30.7% of cases belongs to 18-30 years, 31-40 years, 41-50 years and 51-60 years, respectively. Also there were 59.3% male and 40.7% female participants included.

Table 1: Clinical profile of study participants

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Age group		
18-30 years	21	7.0
31-40 years	85	28.3
41-50 years	102	34.0
51-60 years	92	30.7
Total	300	100.0
Gender		
Male	178	59.3
Female	122	40.7
Total	300	100.0

Based on MMT grades, there were 67%, 19%, 10.3% and 3.7% of cases belong to grade 1, grade 2, grade 3 and grade 4 respectively. Similarly, there were 88.3% of cases had $AASI \leq 0.5$ and 11.7% of cases had $AASI > 0.5$.

Table 2: Proportion of cases based on grades of MMT and AASI

MMT	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 1	201	67.0
Grade 2	57	19.0
Grade 3	31	10.3
Grade 4	11	3.7
Total	300	100.0
AASI	Frequency	Percentage
≤ 0.5	265	88.3
> 0.5	35	11.7
Total	300	100.0

On assessing the association between MMT and AASI in order to predict the difficult intubation, there was a statistically significant association noted.

Table 3: Comparison of MMT and AASI

MMT	AASI		Total	p value
	≤ 0.5	> 0.5		
Grade 1 & 2	254	4	258	<0.0001*
Grade 3 & 4	11	31	42	
Total	265	35	300	

*Significant

On assessing the efficacy of AASI in predicting difficult intubation, Sn, Sp, PPV, NPV and diagnostic efficacy were reported as 95.9%, 88.6%, 98.5%, 73.8% and 95% respectively.

Table 4: Diagnostic efficacy of AASI

Parameters	Value	95% CI
Sensitivity	95.9%	92.7-97.9%
Specificity	88.6%	73.3-96.8%
PPV	98.5%	96.2-99.4%
NPV	73.8%	61.0-83.6%
Diagnostic accuracy	95%	91.9-97.2%

DISCUSSION

According to Mulla SA et al⁹, 31 patients out of 250 had DVL, with 68% having an AASI of >0.5 and 32% having an AASI of <0.5. Of the 219 individuals with EVL, 20 had an AASI greater than 0.5% and 199 had an AASI less than 0.5%. The sensitivity of TMD & AASI and MMP and TMD differed significantly. The specificity, PPV, and NPV of MMP and TMD and TMD and AASI did not differ significantly. They asserted that there was no discernible difference between MMP and AASI in terms of sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV. The value of AASI and TMD as DVL predictors was compared by Nandini CV et al¹⁰. 14% of cases with unexpected DVL occurred. For AASI, the corresponding values were 86.4%, 38.1%, 89.6%, and 31.4% for sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV; for TMHT, the corresponding values were 94.6%, 4.8%, 85.9%, and 12.5%. They stated that there was absolutely no significant link between the two factors to predict the DVL and that AASI was shown to be less sensitive than TMHT.

The goal of Chhaya M et al¹¹. was to evaluate the AASI's predictive value for DVL. Twenty-one percent of the patients had DVL, with ten and eleven male and female patients, respectively. The AASI's observed and reported sensitivity, specificity, and AUC were 98.7%, 71.4%, and 0.851, respectively. AASI fared better as a predictor of DVL than MMT, SMD, TMD, and IID, according to an AUC study. AASI (≥ 0.5) is a good indicator of DVL when performing direct

laryngoscopy. This result implies that AASI might be used clinically to identify patients who might need extra care during intubation procedures.

The objective of Kamranmanash MR et al⁸. was to evaluate the effectiveness of MMT and a novel bedside screening test called AASI. 6.3% of patients had DVL, according to their report. The optimal DVL cutoff value was determined to be $AASI \leq 0.49$. When compared to MMT, AASI demonstrated greater predictive values and a reduced false negative rate. They asserted that AASI might be used to estimate DVL since it was linked to stronger predictive values than MMT. In order to forecast DVL and the amount of time needed to finish each test, Rupesh S. et al¹². compared the accuracy of AASI with ULBT and MMT. They stated that 12% of the patients had DVL. In comparison to MMP and ULBT, AASI was found to have greater accuracy (89.3%), PPV (55%) and specificity (93.2%). The results showed that ULBT had the lowest sensitivity (50%) and MMP had the highest sensitivity (77.8%). The duration of AASI was longer than those of ULBT and MMP. When compared to AASI and ULBT, they find that the MMP is the most rapid and sensitive test for DVL prediction. Compared to MMT and ULBT, AASI has a higher accuracy and odds ratio, making it a superior predictor of DVL. In order to anticipate challenging laryngeal visualization prior to surgery, Bhaktavar J et al¹³. compared the AASI, TMD, and the ULBT. 33 patients were found to have DVL, according to their findings. In contrast to the ULBT, which had a sensitivity of 42.4%, specificity of 87.7%, PPV of 35%, and diagnostic accuracy of 81.25%, the AASI had a higher sensitivity of 93.94%, specificity of 97.58%, PPV of 86.1 %, diagnostic accuracy of 97.1 %, and low false positive rate. The corresponding values for the TMD were 75.76%, 47.34%, 18.66%, and 51.25%, respectively. Consequently, it is suggested that AASI is better at DVL prediction than both TMD and ULBT. AASI was found to be more accurate in predicting difficult intubation than both RHTMD and ULBT, as evidenced by its much larger AUC of ROC. The optimal threshold values for AASI > 0.49 cm, TMD < 21 cm, and ULBT > 2 were recommended to forecast endotracheal intubation difficulty. They stated that it was discovered that DVL could be accurately predicted by the preoperative assessment result of $AASI > 0.49$.

Rajkhowa T et al¹⁴ set out to investigate the AASI's DVL prediction value. They reported that 3.6% of patients had the DVL. They found that the AASI's sensitivity, specificity, and AUC of ROC were, respectively, 81.25, 96.7, and 0.890. It was discovered that AASI's AUC

outperformed MMT, SMD, and TMD. They asserted that with direct laryngoscopy, AASI (≥ 0.5) is a reliable indicator of DVL. The validity of AASI in the evaluation of challenging airway management was evaluated by Chandak VC et al¹⁵. They discovered that 3.6% of patients had DVL. The results of their study showed that the sensitivity and specificity were, respectively, 75% and 95.7%. They asserted that AASI (≥ 0.5) with direct laryngoscopy is a definite marker of DVL. The AASI approach was examined by Nasr-Esfahani M et al¹⁶. to predict difficult laryngoscopy and difficult tracheal intubation. 52 patients experienced challenging endotracheal intubation, while 54 patients had straightforward endotracheal intubation, according to their findings. For endotracheal intubation difficulty prediction with 0.857 AUROC, the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and overall accuracy for AASI in cutoff point 0.515 were 84.6%, 77.7%, 78.5%, 84%, and 81.13%, respectively. Their findings demonstrated the accuracy and high sensitivity and specificity values of AASI in predicting the difficulty of endotracheal intubation; as a result, emergency physicians should be trained in this technique.

CONCLUSION

The AASI is a new yet helpful test to gauge how difficult laryngoscopic visualization will be during tracheal intubation. The relationship between AASI and difficult laryngoscopic visualization is demonstrated in this study, which indicates that higher AASI is likely associated with higher Cormack-Lehane grades and anesthesiologist discomfort.

Declarations

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Conflict of interest: None declared

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